

Information, Communication, and Technology (ICT) Integration in Mathematics Classroom: A Challenge for Nigeria

Ugwu, Solomon Ekene, Onwusi, Gladys Chika, and Mbah, Sylvia Nkem

Department of Science and Computer Education, Faculty of Education, Godfrey Okoye University Enugu,
Nigeria

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13736789>

Abstract: Beyond the school-age population, people must be aware and come to terms with the interplay of technological advancement in all spheres of life endeavours. The management of such advancements needs to be tackled at the instructional levels of the learning enterprise. Information and communication technology (ICT) is a promising practice in mathematics classrooms, but its success depends mainly on several issues, such as teachers' perception of ICT capabilities, teachers' attitudes towards the contribution of ICT to mathematics teaching, and students' understanding of mathematics. The success of ICT integration exercises in mathematics classrooms depends largely on these issues. Despite the many challenges faced, Nigeria has great hopes for improving the outcome of education and learning. This requires the cooperation of policymakers, educators, and stakeholders to improve technology access, provide adequate teacher training and support, align curriculum and assessments with ICT standards, address privacy and security issues, and invest in infrastructure and maintenance. This paper provided an exploratory study that looked into the feasibility of combining ICT with traditional teaching methods in Mathematics Education in Nigeria. The management of this combination lies in the domain of education policies and implementation structures. The study proposed implications and consequences of the integration of ICT in Mathematics Education by exploring plausible causes/scenarios for the performance and disposition of teachers and students towards the use of ICT in teaching mathematics in Nigeria.

Keywords: Challenges, information and communication technology (ICT), integration, mathematics education

Introduction

Since it is a scientific-based course that promotes the acquisition of specialized scientific knowledge and abilities that explain the natural occurrences of living in society, mathematics is known as the queen of all subjects. It is something that develops in civilization in proportion to the rise in population demand (Das, 2019). It began with a real-world issue that needed to be resolved by men. It has aided in the advancement of culture, many academic fields, and civilization. The integration of diverse media, technology, and approaches into the teaching and learning environment is crucial for achieving excellence in education. Teachers and students in the sciences now have more chances thanks to access to a new generation of ICT. However, the familiarity and proficiency of educators with the new resources is necessary for the successful integration of such applications. Although integrating ICT into the planning, testing, and management of instructional tasks is a complex process, it should adhere to a set of guidelines. It also calls for a minimal standard of proficiency from both teachers and pupils. Information and communication technology (ICT) is a promising practice in the mathematics classroom, but its

success will primarily depend on several factors, including teachers' attitudes toward ICT contribution to mathematics teaching, teachers' perceptions of ICT skills, and teachers' attitudes toward students' math learning. Using enthusiasm, confidence, and a sense of control over technology, a math instructor can try to integrate technology into the classroom.

According to recent studies, student outcomes are impacted when teachers use ICT in mathematics classrooms (Hegedus, Tapper, & Dalton, 2016). Merely having technology in the classroom does not translate into better student performance. The decisions made by the instructor regarding the integration of ICT in the mathematics classroom will determine whether student achievements are enhanced. Hegedus et al (2016). Literature has produced a variety of theoretical frameworks to comprehend ICT integration by mathematics instructors, given the significance of the teacher in ICT integration in the classroom. Thus, incorporating ICT into the classroom is a useful step toward the professional development of science and math teachers.

Mathematics Education and Information Communication Technology

From ancient civilizations to contemporary educational systems, mathematics instruction has changed over the ages. Mathematical ideas and techniques were created by ancient societies like Mesopotamia, Egypt, and Greece for use in trade, building, and astronomy. Algebra, geometry, and calculus emerged because mathematics became more codified and abstract throughout the Renaissance. To keep up with the needs of industry and technology, a more methodical approach to mathematics instruction was required after the Industrial Revolution. The 20th century saw the advent of digital technologies and computers, which completely changed many facets of life, including education. Data processing, communication, and information access were all revolutionized by the emergence of computers, the internet, and digital gadgets. ICT gave educators and students access to a wealth of materials and information, opening up new avenues for teaching and learning (Nworgu & Onyema, 2018).

It has been determined that information and communication technology (ICT) could be used to improve math instruction. In recent years, the use of ICT in mathematics has gained ground among mathematics instructors as many of them have to see the usefulness of incorporating ICT use in teaching and learning of mathematics in various studies. It has been found that using ICT in mathematics education allows students to explore mathematical concepts in fresh and interactive ways, resulting in higher levels of cognitive growth. For example, a study conducted in 2002 by Borko and Eisenhart found that using technological aids, such graphing calculators, can help students understand mathematical concepts better and promote active learning. Similar to this, Hohenwarter (2009) study discovered that employing dynamic mathematics software, such as Geogebra, can increase conceptual understanding and enhance students' exploration of mathematical ideals.

Mathematicians generally teach their subjects by rote memorization and abstract explanations, which can be difficult for pupils to understand. The abstract character of mathematics and its lack of application to real-world situations cause many pupils to struggle with it. It has been shown that integrating ICT into math classes has a major impact on students' growth. Whether or whether ICT use will help students learn mathematics will depend on the teacher's involvement in selecting when, how, and where to use it. The uptake of ICT integration has demonstrated that the elements influencing ICT integration are classified into three paradigms: the teacher-technology interaction, the teacher-technology interaction and the environment the teacher operates in, and the interaction between the teacher's beliefs, capacity for ICT competency enhancement, and their surroundings (Nworgu & Onyema, 2018).

By offering visual aids, interactive exercises, and real-world applications, ICT integration in mathematics education tackles these issues and makes mathematics more approachable and interesting. ICT improves math instruction by encouraging problem-solving techniques, conceptual comprehension, and active learning. Mathematics teachers have historically been especially concerned about the use of ICT in the classroom. A few instances of ICT being used in mathematics are databases, spreadsheets, specialist software, computerized graphing, graphic calculators, and portable devices. These educators can optimize the use of ICT in mathematics education by utilizing it as a tool for instruction. Students are taught to work in collaborative groups or apply the problem-solving process when using a computer to solve a problem, and then ICT is involved in developing the solution. Higher-order thinking of math students consists of the transformation of information and concepts. Students' skills in the use and application of mathematics are frequently enhanced when they utilize ICT as a tool to help them find information, solve issues, or comprehend what's going on. ICT can be a powerful and effective tool, but for students to take full use of the opportunities presented to them, they must acquire the necessary technical skills. The way teachers present material and students interact with mathematical ideas has been completely transformed by the incorporation of ICT into mathematics education. Brinda et al (2019).

Theoretical Background

Social Constructivism Theory

According to Lev Vygotsky's social constructivism theory, learning is a social process that happens as a result of interactions between students and their surroundings (Vygotsky, 1978). This notion holds that students build their knowledge through their interactions with those around them. Through social interactions, learners can assimilate novel concepts and perspectives that mold their worldview.

Technology and Social Constructivism Theory for Teaching Mathematics

With the use of technology in the classroom, students can work together with their instructors and peers, access a multitude of resources, and interact creatively and innovatively with the course materials. ICT has completely changed how we communicate and learn from one another. By enabling students to participate in a community of practice, develop their knowledge, and engage in collaborative learning, ICT supports the ideas of social constructivism theory (Jonassen, 2000).

Collaborative Learning: A keystone of social constructivism theory is collaborative learning. This notion holds that students build their knowledge through social interactions. By giving students the means to interact and work together with teachers and classmates to solve mathematical issues, ICT can support collaborative learning. Online chat rooms, discussion boards, and collaborative writing tools, for instance, can facilitate collaborative learning by enabling students to participate in discussions, exchange ideas, and create knowledge collectively.

Constructing Knowledge: According to the social constructivism theory, students build their knowledge through interactions with their surroundings. ICT can help with this process by giving students access to a variety of tools, resources, and educational materials. For instance, interactive multimedia, virtual worlds, and online simulations can enable students to build and explore their understanding of mathematical topics in a more dynamic and captivating manner (Jonassen, 2000).

Community of practice: A community of practice is an association of people who participate in learning activities together and have a shared interest or objective. According to the social constructivism hypothesis, students can build their own knowledge by engaging with a community of practice. By giving students the means to cooperate, exchange ideas, and pool resources, ICT can help establish a community of practice. Social media

sites, online learning communities, and discussion forums, for instance, can help foster the development of a community of practice in mathematics teaching.

Factors Affecting the Integration of ICT into Mathematics Education In Nigeria

ICT use in the classroom is necessary to raise academic standards and improve learning outcomes. ICT use can support the development of 21st century skills including problem-solving, cooperation, and communication. The use of ICT tools can improve teaching and learning outcomes by providing access to digital tools and resources. In addition, social justice and equitable issues can be helped by integrating ICT into the classroom. ICT integration in mathematics education can improve the educational opportunities for pupils from disadvantaged backgrounds and raise their chances of success in the real world. Nonetheless, the following elements may have an impact on integration of ICT into mathematical education in Nigeria:

Teacher's Expertise and Abilities

The effective use of ICT in mathematics education depends on the knowledge and abilities of teachers. A high degree of ICT expertise and proficiency is needed on the side of the teacher in order to integrate ICT in the classroom. This involves being familiar with a variety of ICT tools and resources, having pedagogical expertise to utilize ICT effectively, and being able to use ICT to improve instruction. It's also critical that educators help students advance their digital literacy. Studies have indicated that there is a wide variation in the ICT skills and knowledge of educators. Despite the fact that many teachers use technology in the classroom. Ottenbreit-Leftwich et al. (2010).

According to Ottenbreit-Leftwich et al. (2010), only few of them have the ICT skills and knowledge needed to properly integrate technology into the mathematics curriculum. Similarly, even though Ertmer et al. (2012) stated that teachers' ICT knowledge and skills are typically limited, they had positive attitudes on the use of ICT in education. The proficiency of math teachers has a significant impact on the incorporation of ICT in the classroom. High ICT knowledge and proficiency teachers are more likely to increase student-centred learning and use ICT in the classroom in new ways. Additionally, teachers with successful advanced ICT knowledge and skills are more likely to assist pupils in becoming more digitally literate. Ertmer et al (2012). To enable the successful integration of ICT in mathematics education, it is crucial to give teachers the training and support they need to advance their ICT knowledge and abilities.

Teachers' Perspectives on the Integration of ICT into Mathematics Education

Teachers' attitudes on ICT are crucial to the effective integration of this technology in mathematics teaching. Teachers' attitudes play a major role in whether ICT integration in education is successful or not. Teachers are excited about the prospect of utilizing ICT integration more effectively in their lessons, which will lead to improved learning results. However, less often utilization of these tools by teachers who have a bad attitude toward ICT integration has an adverse effect on student learning. According to (Lai and Law, 2018), a multitude of factors can impact educators' perspectives on the integration of ICT. These include the pedagogical views of instructors, their degree of expertise, how valuable they think ICT tools are for teaching and learning, and any perceived barriers to adopting them.

Teachers who possess both strong pedagogical ideas and excellent ICT skills, for example, are more likely to see ICT integration favourably than teachers who lack both of these attributes. The way educators feel about integrating ICT can have a big impact on how effective instruction is. Positive attitudes toward ICT integration

are associated with instructors' more effective use of ICT tools, which raises student motivation, engagement, and learning outcomes (Lai and Law, 2018). Teachers that have a bad attitude toward ICT integration, on the other hand, typically stick to traditional teaching strategies that might not be as successful in energizing and inspiring their pupils.

Benefits of ICT to Learning Mathematics in Modern Era

ICT integration into mathematics education improves instruction, fosters student participation and teamwork, and equips students for success in a technologically advanced society. Teachers can design engaging and meaningful learning experiences that enable students to develop into competent and self-assured mathematicians by skilfully utilizing ICT tools. Numerous advantages come with integrating ICT into mathematics education, such as improved conceptual comprehension and visualization, higher motivation and engagement, individualized learning, access to a wealth of learning resources, and chances for problem-solving and real-world application. Ruthven (2013). These advantages highlighted how crucial it is to use ICT to support efficient teaching and learning of mathematics in the current digital environment.

Enhanced Conceptual Understanding and Visualization

For the pupil, visualizing is the most challenging task. It takes a while to draw a single diagram, and in order to ensure accuracy, the learner must comprehend how the design is constructed or transformed. A modification can be made by the learner using dynamic geometry software. After that, users can alter the image's shape and observe the result. They are able to alter the mirror line's location and observe the results. They are able to shift the centre of rotation with rotations. They will develop an image in their minds of what transitions entail in this way. Ruthven (2013)

ICT tools let students see mathematical ideas in a concrete way. Examples of these tools are simulation programs and dynamic graphing software. Students can explore abstract mathematical concepts with the use of interactive images, which develops their conceptual comprehension. Students can modify geometric shapes and functions using software such as GeoGebra, which enables them to investigate mathematical relationships in real time and observe the results of modifications. Angle relationships can be investigated by students. They can measure a triangle's three angles and determine that they always add up to 180° . They can swiftly check many various triangles by moving any one of the vertices. For the student, this is a very convincing demonstration. Nworgu et al (2018). However, they can extend this idea, by constructing diagrams and looking for interesting relationships. They can check them by dragging the points. If they find something, they should leave the computer and try to prove the relationship using geometry

A Rise in Motivation and Engagement

Research has indicated that the integration of ICT into mathematics education enhances students' motivation and enthusiasm for the subject matter. Students can actively participate in the learning process through interactive learning experiences offered by ICT (Johnson, 2016). Access to a wide range of educational tools and materials for arithmetic instruction and learning is made possible by ICT. To enhance classroom instruction, a plethora of instructional films, tutorials, practice activities, and learning materials are available on digital platforms, educational websites, and digital libraries. This improves students' learning chances outside of the classroom by giving them access to resources at any time and from any location. Students are encouraged to participate and learn by using educational games, quizzes, and activities that make mathematics learning entertaining and

pleasurable. There are a ton of software games and activities available that are intended to aid students in understanding specific mathematical concepts.

These can occasionally take the shape of lesson plans complete with exercises and examples. Additional instances take the shape of computer games, when players must solve mathematical puzzles in order to advance. Lastly, certain examples—such as transformational geometry—offer mathematical environments in which users can investigate a certain subject and alter particular characteristics. Students can collaborate on mathematical activities and projects with the use of ICT in collaborative learning environments. Students can work together to solve problems in real time, discuss ideas, and cooperate using online collaboration platforms like Microsoft Teams or Google Docs. Students benefit from peer learning, communication skills, and teamwork as a result of this. Ruthven (2013).

Individualized Education and Distinction

The content and difficulty levels of educational software and platforms that are adaptive are modified in response to the performance and advancement of pupils. This enables educators to give instruction that is specifically suited to the needs of each student. Dream-Box Learning is an example of adaptive math software that adjusts to each student's unique learning rate and offers focused encouragement and feedback. With the use of dynamic math software, students can investigate mathematical concepts. Students can construct mathematical functions, statements, or diagrams and investigate how adjustments will affect them. Personalized and customized instruction can be provided to pupils based on their individual learning needs thanks to ICT. Adaptive learning capabilities are available in educational software and apps, which modify content and difficulty levels according to students' performance and advancement. This enables teachers to provide targeted support and challenge for each student, ensuring that all learners are appropriately challenged (Stoilescu, 2014).

Real Life Application and Problem Solving

With the use of ICT technologies, students may solve real-world problems and apply mathematical ideas to situations. ICT facilitates the connection between practical applications of mathematics and abstract mathematical ideas. Students can apply mathematical principles in real-world contexts by exploring real-world scenarios through educational software and simulations, such as financial modelling, data analysis, and engineering simulations. Students are better prepared for future professions in STEM sectors and are encouraged to strengthen their critical thinking skills. Students can draw links between mathematics and the real world with the use of data analysis tools and mathematical modelling software (Stoilescu, 2014). ICT makes it easier to monitor student progress and give timely feedback by enabling the use of digital assessment tools and platforms. Students study real-world data sets and do statistical analyses using programs like Python and Excel, which helps them become more adept at solving problems. Teachers can evaluate students' learning quickly and effectively with the help of online tests, interactive exercises, and automatic grading systems. This makes it possible for teachers to pinpoint students' areas of strength and weakness, offer focused feedback, and modify their lesson plans to suit their requirements (Das et al., 2019).

Challenges and Considerations of ICT in Mathematics Education in Nigeria

Although there are several challenges that must be solved, ICT integration in mathematics education has the potential to be advantageous. For example, teachers may need extra support and training to appropriately integrate technology into their teaching practices. In addition, infrastructure problems like restricted access to technology

may make it more difficult to use ICT in the classroom. ICT has the power to revolutionize mathematics education in Nigeria, but to fully reap its reward; several issues need to be resolved. It would be essential to address concerns about infrastructure, privacy and security, cultural considerations, curriculum alignment, teacher preparation, and access to technology to successfully integrate ICT into mathematics instruction in Nigeria (Das et al., 2019).

Digital Divide and Technology Access

The accessibility of ICT is essential to its incorporation in mathematics education. To integrate ICT in mathematics education, hardware and software must be accessible. Educational institutions frequently lack the software and hardware required for ICT integration to be successful. This lack of accessibility may make it more difficult for ICT to be adopted and applied in mathematics instruction. Socioeconomic factors also affect how easily accessible ICT technologies are. Nigeria confronts formidable obstacles when it comes to granting access to technology, especially in remote and underprivileged regions (Agboola & Ojokheta, 2019). Basic ICT infrastructure including computers, internet access, and energy are lacking in many schools (Njoku, 2016). Inequalities in access to ICT resources and opportunities are made worse by the digital gap between urban and rural areas (Akinsolu, 2016). Low-income communities may have limited access to ICT technologies due to poverty and inadequate infrastructure. This lack of accessibility could exacerbate the digital divide and make it more difficult for students to use ICT fairly in the classroom.

Professional Development and Training for Teachers

Effective technology integration in instruction is hampered by mathematics instructors' limited ICT proficiency (Agboola & Ojokheta, 2019). To use ICT tools and software in mathematics instruction effectively, teachers need to be trained and supported (Nworgu & Onyema, 2018). Improving teachers' ICT competencies is hampered by inadequate money and resources for teacher training programs (Akinsolu, 2016).

Combining Assessment and Curriculum

The national curriculum and assessment criteria are frequently not aligned with ICT integration in mathematics education (Nworgu & Onyema, 2018). Curriculum frameworks must be updated to incorporate ICT-based learning objectives and assessments (Agboola & Ojokheta, 2019). Teachers face difficulties while creating ICT-based classes due to the scarcity of digital resources that are in line with the curriculum (Njoku, 2016).

Security and Privacy Issues

When students use online resources and platforms, their personal information is at danger due to inadequate data privacy and security procedures (Nworgu & Onyema, 2018). Schools and other educational institutions are concerned about cybersecurity threats such malware, phishing attacks, and data breaches (Agboola & Ojokheta, 2019). Policies and procedures are required to protect students' privacy and guarantee the security of the ICT infrastructure in educational institutions (Akinsolu, 2016).

Socioeconomic and Cultural Factors

In Nigerian society, views toward technology and education are influenced by socio cultural variables (Akinsolu, 2016). ICT acceptance and use in Mathematics Education may be impacted by cultural practices and attitudes (Njoku, 2016). Access to ICT resources and opportunities is impacted by socioeconomic inequality, especially for vulnerable communities (Agboola & Ojokheta, 2019).

Infrastructure and Service

The sustainability of ICT projects in schools is challenged by inadequate infrastructure and poor maintenance (Nworgu & Onyema, 2018). ICT-enabled teaching and learning activities are disrupted by power outages and

unstable electrical supplies (Akinsolu, 2016). To guarantee the successful integration of ICT in Mathematics instruction, schools need to provide continuous assistance and make investments in infrastructure maintenance (Njoku, 2016).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

ICT integration in mathematics education in Nigeria necessitates a comprehensive strategy that considers both the advantages and disadvantages. Nigeria can improve the standard of mathematics instruction, provide students with critical 21st-century skills, and support national development by utilizing ICT efficiently. Nigeria has enormous potential for raising teaching and learning standards, despite its many obstacles. Digital libraries, online courses, and instructional websites are just a few of the many educational tools and materials that may be accessed with ICT. These materials enhance and augment what is taught in the classroom for the benefit of the students. Additionally, it makes problem-solving and real-world applications easier, preparing them for professions in a culture that is driven by technology. Through interactive tools and simulations, it also improves conceptual understanding and visualization of mathematical topics. Most significantly, it creates individualized learning experiences catered to each student's unique needs, encouraging differentiated instruction and taking into account a variety of learning styles. This helps students understand concepts more deeply and become more engaged in the process of learning. Notwithstanding these advantages, the difficulties associated with ICT integration in mathematics education must be addressed. Policymakers, educators, and other stakeholders must work together to increase access to technology, support and train teachers appropriately, ensure that curriculum and assessments adhere to ICT standards, handle privacy and security issues, and make maintenance and infrastructure investments.

Recommendations

The integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in mathematics education in Nigeria offers significant potential for enhancing the quality of education and equipping students with essential skills for the 21st century. The adoption of ICT in mathematics education can transform the learning experience by providing access to a vast array of digital resources, including online courses, instructional websites, and digital libraries. These resources complement traditional classroom instruction and offer students a richer, more diverse learning environment. Furthermore, the use of ICT facilitates problem-solving and the application of mathematical concepts to real-world scenarios, which is crucial for preparing students for future careers in a technology-driven world.

Interactive tools and simulations enabled by ICT can significantly enhance students' conceptual understanding and visualization of mathematical topics. By tailoring learning experiences to individual needs, ICT supports differentiated instruction and accommodates various learning styles, leading to deeper engagement and understanding. However, the successful integration of ICT in mathematics education requires addressing several challenges. It is essential for policymakers, educators, and stakeholders to collaborate on improving access to technology, providing adequate training and support for teachers, ensuring that curricula and assessments are aligned with ICT standards, and addressing privacy and security concerns. Additionally, ongoing investment in infrastructure and maintenance is critical to sustaining the effectiveness of ICT in education.

References

- Agboola, A. J., & Ojokheta, K. O. (2019). Challenges of integration of information and communication technology in mathematics teaching and learning in Nigerian secondary schools. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 9(5), 147-155.
- Akinsolu, A. O. (2016). Digital divide in Nigerian schools: Issues and solutions. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1482.
- Borko, H., & Eisenhart, M. (2002). Learning to teach with technology: A reflective look at professional development. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 26(3), 265-290.
- Brinda, T., Raghavendra, G., & Deshpande, S. (2019). Integration of ICT in mathematics teaching at pre-service teacher education level. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 10(17), 112-119.
- Das, K. (2019). Role of ICT for better mathematics teaching. *Shanlax International Journal of Education*, 7(4), 19-28.
- Das, K., & Roy, D. (2019). Applications of mathematical knowledge in history, geography, fine arts & physical education subjects in two-year B.Ed. program: Indian context. *Journal of Emerging Technology and Innovative Research*, 6(6), 8-15.
- Das, K., & Roy, D. (2019). Infrastructural facility faced by trainee teachers in new two-year B.Ed. program in West Bengal. *International Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, 9(7), 210-222.
- Ertmer, P. A., & Ottenbreit-Leftwich, A. T. (2010). Teacher technology change: How knowledge, confidence, beliefs, and culture intersect. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 42(3), 255-284.
- Handal, B., Campbell, C., Cavanagh, M., Petocz, P., & Kelly, N. (2013). Technological pedagogical content knowledge of secondary mathematics teachers. *Contemporary Issues in Technology and Teacher Education*, 13(1), 22-40.
- Hegedus, S., Tapper, J., & Dalton, S. (2016). Exploring how teacher-related factors relate to student achievement in learning advanced algebra in technology-enhanced classrooms. *Journal of Mathematics Teacher Education*, 19(1), 7-32.
- Hohenwarter, M., & Jones, A. (2009). The dynamic mathematics software GeoGebra as an e-learning tool for mathematics education. In A. Tatnall & A. Jones (Eds.), *Education and technology for a better world: 9th IFIP TC 3 World Conference on Computers in Education, WCCE 2009, Bento Gonçalves, Brazil, July 27-31, 2009*. Proceedings (pp. 462-471). Springer.

- Jonassen, D. H. (2000). Toward a design theory of problem solving. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 48(4), 63-85.
- Lai, K. W., & Law, N. (2018). An impact analysis of an ICT-medical approach to teaching English: Tutors' perspectives. *Educational Technology & Society*, 21(2), 135-148.
- Njoku, Z. C. (2016). ICT as an instructional tool in teaching and learning mathematics: An appraisal of teachers' challenges in Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(21), 138-146.
- Nworgu, L. N., & Onyema, J. J. (2018). Teachers' perception of the integration of information and communication technology in the teaching of mathematics in Nigerian secondary schools. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 9(4), 1-8.
- Ruthven, K. (2013). Frameworks for analysing the expertise that underpins successful integration of digital technologies into everyday teaching practice. Paper presented at the Annual Meeting of the American Educational Research Association, San Francisco, CA.
- Stoilescu, D. (2014). Studying challenges in integrating technology in secondary mathematics with technological pedagogical and content knowledge (TPACK). In P. Kommers, T. Issa, T. Issa, D. Chang, & P. Isias (Eds.), *Proceedings of the International Conferences on Education Technologies and Sustainability, Technology and Education* (pp. 59-66). New Taipei City, Taiwan.